

The Woman As an active element in Security and Peace According to UN Security Council Resolution No 1325

Dhuha Nashat Namuk

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 13, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: December 15, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Women , UN Security Council Resolution 1325, Peace</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7439013</p>	<p><i>Women and girls are among the groups most vulnerable to the violation of their rights in the normal situation, and these risks and violations increase in the event of armed conflicts, so it was necessary to provide legal protection for them through international agreements, resolutions and declarations, and mere recognition and recognition of the rights of women and girls is not enough, but rather To involve women in the decision-making process and to participate in all aspects of economic and political life. Through this research paper, the rights granted to women and the mechanisms for their protection and their involvement in international peace and security operations were highlighted, and the tools provided by UN Security Council Resolution 1325, legal obligations and the pillars stemming from this resolution were highlighted.</i></p>

Introduction

On October 31, 2000, the United Nations Security Council adopted Resolution 1325 on women, security and peace unanimously, stressing the importance and effectiveness of the role of women in conflict prevention as well as their role in peace building.

The resolution also affirmed that women and children are the groups most vulnerable to harm as a result of armed conflict as a result of their constant targeting and the practice of violence and discrimination against them by armed elements.

Resolution 1325 is one of the resolutions of great importance at the international level, as its promulgation was represented by the United Nations Security Council, which dominates the world and not only the United Nations, which gives the resolution the status of obligation, and the content of this resolution has embodied women in their highest form as an effective member of the issue of maintaining security and peace.

According to the above, it can be said that achieving sustainable peace requires an integrated approach based on specific criteria based on achieving coherence and complementarity between security and political measures at the same time, in addition to development and human rights, especially in the field of gender equality and the rule of law.^[1]

The above is the most embodied approach to Security Council resolution 1325, where this UN resolution was one of the milestones regarding the rights of girls and women and everything related to their issues, where the aforementioned resolution is one of the most important and important achievements of the Security Council, where women and girls are among the groups most vulnerable to violations of their rights in the normal situation and these risks and violations increase in the event of armed conflicts, so it was necessary to provide them with legal protection through International conventions, resolutions and declarations, and the mere recognition and recognition of the rights of women and girls is not enough, but it was necessary to involve women in the decision-making process and participate in all aspects of economic and political life.

In addition to Resolution 1325, the Security Council has adopted several resolutions related to the concept of this resolution to constitute strong support for women regardless of their age, colors, nationalities and ethnicity, even if the implementation of these resolutions took relatively long periods of time due to political, economic and social changes in addition to things that may hinder the implementation of these resolutions related to security instability.

Through this research paper, we will talk about the concept of Security Council Resolution 1325 and the extent of its necessity and importance, in addition to explaining the mechanisms of women's participation under it, by dividing the research paper into two sections.

The Importance of the study

The importance of this study highlights the importance of the rights granted to women and the mechanisms for their protection and involvement in international peace and security operations and the statement of what tools were granted by Security Council resolution 1325, legal obligations and the sub-pillars of this resolution.

Study Methodology

The descriptive and analytical approach was followed by describing and analyzing the provisions of Security Council Resolution 1325 on Women, Security and Peace.

The statement of the Problem

The problem of research arises primarily that despite the fact that despite the provisions of international law of human rights in general and the rights of women in particular, these rights are nothing more than ink on paper due to the absence of obligation or penalty for their non-application, in addition to the fact that these rights organized in international conventions are still subject to violation due to the weakness of the oversight and supervisory bodies or the implementation of the provisions of the conventions at the national level.

The international reality indicates the need to have real mechanisms that contribute to providing protection and activation of the role of women through this study we will highlight one of the most important of these mechanisms in addition to indicating their effectiveness on the ground.

Study difficulties

The difficulties are the paucity of literature on UNSCR 1325 and the lack of sufficient references to address the issue.

Section one : What is Security Council Resolution 1325?

The role of women in achieving security and Islam is one of the most important issues that have attracted wide attention, where women must be seen as a key partner in promoting the values of peace in society, and accordingly Security Council resolution 1325 considered women as an active element in security and peace.

First Requirement: The Concept of Security Council Resolution 1325

On 31 October 2000, the Security Council adopted Resolution 1325, which contained a set of key points relating to women and the gravity of the various violations to which they are subjected during armed conflict^[2]

The resolution noted the importance of women's equal and full participation in contributing to peace negotiations and peace and peacekeeping, as well as contributing to post-conflict reconstruction^[3].

UNSCR 1325 also stressed the importance of women's equal participation in all efforts aimed at maintaining and promoting security and peace.

Resolution No. 1325 urged all actors to increase women's participation and integrate the concept of gender into all UN peacekeeping efforts. In addition, the resolution called on all parties to conflict to take special measures to protect women and girls from gender-based violence during armed conflict through women's participation in decision-making and in peace processes. Their participation in all peacekeeping efforts as well as the need to increase the role of women in decision-making on conflict prevention and resolution. On the integration of a gender perspective of training into a peacekeeping operation

Despite the international community's slowness in involving women in peacekeeping and peace building operations, Security Council Resolution 1325 made peace a title and stressed that it is difficult to achieve equality and development in the absence of peace, so it was necessary to focus on any obstacle that threatens security and stability, as it can be concluded that Islam in the context of the Security Council resolution can have its meaning lies in the political process and adherence to human rights after the war. Women are indispensable in peacekeeping plans and workmanship. This is in addition to the need to involve women in peacekeeping operations, so the United Nations Security Council Resolution 1325 followed a new form of involvement of women through their involvement in the security and military fields, aiming to activate their participation in the maintenance of security and peace, as the protection of women has been based in accordance with UN Security Council Resolution 1325 on the need to protect the rights of women. For women and girls during and after armed conflicts, stressing the need to apply human rights laws. With regard to gender mainstreaming, the United Nations programs and reports are the concept of a gender perspective according to the Economic and Social Council of the United Nations as the process of assessing the contributions of women and men to any planned work, including legislation, policies or programs at all regions and levels, and is therefore a strategy for the empowerment of women in various fields and the main objective of which is to achieve gender equality^[4]

The researcher believes that all of the above, despite its importance, but Security Council resolution 1325 on women and peace has not received the required application on the ground, where there are still large gaps in its application, especially in the Arab region in general and in Iraq in particular, for several reasons, the most

prominent of which may be that women in the Arab world and in Iraq in particular do not have equal votes in decision-making at all levels, including peace talks.

Second Requirement: The Mandatory Nature of UNSCR 1325

Article 25 of the Charter of the United Nations provides as follows: "Members of the United Nations undertake to accept and implement the resolutions of the Security Council in accordance with this Charter." By extrapolating this article, it can be said that it is the key or cornerstone to answer the following question: Is UNSCR 1325 a binding resolution or not?

The provisions of Article 25 are included under the provisions of Chapter V of the Charter of the United Nations, where part of the jurisprudence holds that any Security Council resolution not issued under the provisions of Article VII, which is the chapter dealing with coercive measures, is not binding, i.e. in the sense that any Security Council resolution that does not fall within the provisions of Article VII is not binding, since Security Council resolutions are binding only when they are enforcement authorities in relation to a subject that threatens international peace and security, or In the event of a breach of international peace, and under the foregoing, the mandate of the Security Council under the provisions of Chapter VI, i.e. under Articles 33, 34 and 36, is limited to assisting Member States to reach a peaceful agreement with minimal interference, which constitutes a non-binding recommendation for the peaceful settlement of disputes^[5]

Another aspect of the jurisprudence also holds that Resolution 1325 was enacted under Chapter VI of the Charter of the United Nations and that the provisions of Resolution 1325 are only morally binding. Proponents of this trend assert that "substantive decisions do not impose the same binding obligations as decisions taken in response to threats to international peace or security."^[6]

In the light of the above, the researcher believes that the phrase "threat to peace" needs to be interpreted more broadly, its concept is highly developed, and under these circumstances it is not permissible to interpret this phrase narrowly within the limits of the use of armed force only, but we hope that the transition to the broad concept or its interpretation in a way that allows for greater flexibility in the event of the application of the text of article 25.

The researcher also believes that Security Council Resolution 1325 when looking closely at extrapolating its provisions it is possible to say that there is no order confirming the issuance of the resolution under Chapter VI where there are some articles that have an impact and relationship with the provisions of Chapter VII, for example, paragraph 6 of Security Council Resolution 1325 dealt with the issue of training military personnel and civilian police personnel in preparation for their deployment in conflict zones, which means that this resolution relates to and has a strong impact on the provisions of the item Seventh, since the general origin is that the deployment of troops can only be made after the Security Council has determined that there is a threat to international peace and security.

In addition to the above, it can be said that even if Resolution 1325 is only a product of Chapter VI, there is no clear written rule stating that Security Council resolutions created under Chapter VI are non-binding and that the resolutions contained in Chapter VII are binding.

A binding resolution can be taken under Chapter VI (just as non-binding resolutions can be made under Chapter VII^[7]) So it can be argued that if Resolution 1325 is passed under Chapter VI, it is not necessarily non-binding Article 24 grants the Security Council permission to act on behalf of States Members of the United Nations to maintain international peace and security through the application of the powers covered in Chapters VI and VII and this means that the overall context of Article 25 in the light of Security Council resolutions can be binding under Chapter VI resolutions.

Given the scope of application of Article 25, and through the practice of the Charter of the United Nations, we find that in no case has the Security Council defined the scope of the obligation of the Members of the United Nations under Article 25, nor has it expressly indicated on any occasion that a particular resolution should or should not be considered to fall under that Article accordingly, Article 25 may apply to resolutions under Chapters VI and VII irrespective of any chapter of the Chapters. The Charter applies to Resolution 1325, the binding nature of Article 25 must also be applied, making it binding on States.

If article 25 applies to decisions under Chapter VI, it is important to identify limited, and perhaps rare, cases in which a binding decision can be taken under Chapter VI.

It should be noted that the language of the resolution plays a prominent role in determining the extent to which it is obligatory, so it is necessary to carefully consider and analyze the language of the Security Council resolution before reaching a conclusion on its binding impact.

In the light of the nature of the powers of Article 25, the question must be identified in each case, taking into account the conditions of the resolution to be interpreted and what the provisions of the Charter were based and, in general, on all the circumstances that might help determine the legal consequences of the Security Council resolution and therefore, to determine the intention of the Security Council to adopt a resolution, at least three factors must be assessed: the language used in the resolution, the discussions that led to it, and the provisions of

the Charter on which it was based. The fourth factor is by addressing the invocation of international laws and standards, including the application of treaties, customary law and jus cogens, among others.

The language of decisions can be classified as either weak or strong. Weak language can indicate the non-binding nature of the decision and strong language can indicate binding intent. Words like "decide," "declares," and "requests" are examples of strong language, while "urge," "recommends," and "encourages" are weak. Resolution 1325 uses a combination of weak and strong language. Weak language includes "induction" and "encouragement".

For example, in paragraph 2, resolution "[e] urges the Secretary-General to implement his strategic plan of action.

"While in paragraph 3, the Secretary-General urges the appointment of more women as special representatives and envoys to conduct good offices on his behalf. On the other hand, among the strong language used is "call", which can also refer to a binding obligation where the Security Council can use weaker language such as "recommends". For example, under paragraph 8, the resolution requires all relevant actors, when negotiating and implementing peace agreements, to adopt a gender perspective Paragraph 9 also calls upon all parties to an armed conflict to fully respect international law applicable to the rights and protection of women and girls as civilians."

From the foregoing, it can be seen that the language used in Resolution 1325 contains strong and weak elements, where the assertion that the language of the resolution makes it in short a binding resolution because it authorizes acts within the limits of the Charter of the United Nations and other international laws.

In addition to the strong foundation of Resolution 1325 by showing that the international community has been interested and interested in women and conflict issues for some time. Therefore, Resolution 1325 is the product of multiple forums through which the importance of the legal status of women and girls in post-conflict situations can be clarified.

Section two : Mechanisms for Activating Security Council Resolution 1325 in Iraq

Iraq has witnessed for many years several conflicts that have stretched from the eighties of the last furnace to the present day, women were the most harmful, most often they are the ones who face the difficulties of life, they are the ones who have been displaced and displaced, and they are the ones who lost the breadwinner for their families, so it was necessary to identify the mechanisms of activating the Security Council resolution and review the legal and constitutional provisions related to women, security and peace (the first requirement) and then move on to the statement of the national action plan adopted by Iraq to activate this resolution (the second requirement)

First Requirement: Constitutional and Legal Provisions on Women, Security and Peace

Legal and constitutional provisions can be defined as the set of principles and rules that relate to the foundations on which the state is based and related to the organization of governance and its biography, the Iraqi Constitution in force for the year 2005 dealt in its preamble with the issues of women and children and attention to them and the spread of a culture of diversity as emphasized through its articles that affirmed the principle of equality before the law without discrimination on the basis of sex^[8], He also affirmed that male and female citizens have the right to participate politically and enjoy all political rights including the right to vote, vote and to be elected^[9], and explicitly referred to the protection of motherhood, childhood and old age^[10], the prohibition of slavery, the slave trade, trafficking in women and children and sex trafficking^[11]. The electoral law should include a representation of women of at least a quarter of the number of members of the House of Representatives^[12]

The Iraqi Constitution required the promulgation of complementary laws to regulate other matters to protect women and their effective participation, including laws related to freedom of opinion and media, peaceful demonstration, the establishment of parties and the prevention of violence and arbitrariness.

As for the legal provisions, the Iraqi legal system has dealt with a set of laws supporting women, but the real problem lies in the actual application of these laws, for example, the law on combating trafficking in human beings stipulated the need to establish a central committee from several ministries, but the problem and the allocation of special texts for the protection of women related to the case of victims of human trafficking, but there are no care homes to receive victims of human trafficking, and a law has been adopted to allow women to work in the agencies. For example, article 41 of the amended Iraqi Penal Code provides for the authority to discipline the husband for his wife, where this text allows assault on wives in all forms of beatings under the pretext of discipline, as stipulated in the Penal Code Article 41 still allows the husband to discipline his wife. The husband may even cause harm to his wife, whether it is psychological or physical.

Article 128 also stipulates that legal excuses are either exempt from punishment or mitigated and are considered a mitigating excuse for committing the crime for reasons of honors or on the basis of a serious provocation by the victim. Matrimonial home.

On the other hand, the legislator stipulates in article 409 that a man must be given a mitigating excuse in the event that he kills his wife or one of his incest if she is in a state of adultery.

Second requirement: Iraq's National Action Plan for the Implementation of the Security Council Resolution on Women, Security and Peace

As a result of the adoption of Security Council resolution 1325 of 2000, there have been many attempts to implement and implement this resolution, although 22 years have passed since the adoption of this resolution, the efforts to enforce it are still moving timidly and there are many gaps related to its implementation, despite that the national efforts in Iraq have been clear in seeking to implement the Security Council resolution on the equal involvement of women in promoting all efforts to adopt a national plan of action for the implementation of this resolution. Resolution 1325

Iraq adopted a national plan for the implementation of UN Security Council Resolution No. 1325 in April 2014 on 1/4/2014 and accordingly Iraq became one of the first countries in the Middle East and North Africa to adopt a national plan to activate the resolution, a point to be counted for the regionalization of Iraq[13], this plan was adopted and developed in partnership with civil society institutions, members of the federal government, representatives of ministries, members of the Federal House of Representatives and legal experts.

The National Plan is based on a set of principles, the most important of which is the recognition of the principle of de facto gender equality in addition to the recognition of all universal human rights of women and all that is stipulated in international conventions, these goals are linked to the need to reach specific results that are measurable and objectively verified and that is constrained by a time frame and a clear distribution of responsibilities, tasks and evaluation. [14]

This plan dealt with specific objectives of working to increase the effective participation of women in decision-making positions and in reconciliation committees and peacebuilding negotiations, in addition to the need to establish a quota for women in the executive branch in order to enable women to exercise their role in the decision-making process, and the plan also included working to harmonize domestic legislation to international standards to ensure the rights of women and human beings in general and amending and repealing all texts that are considered a violation of women's rights, but the researcher believes in this regard that Despite the acknowledgement of this, there has not been actually work to implement what was addressed in the national plan, the discriminatory texts against women in the Iraqi legislative system still exist and no law has been passed to add double protection for women, on the contrary, women are still killed and their rights are violated under the names of honor killings and the intelligent authority is still exercised against women under the Iraqi Penal Code, which allowed the husband the right to discipline his wife.

The National Plan also pointed to the need to empower women and enhance their capacities through a rights-based approach, and here the researcher emphasizes the role played by the Ministry of Higher Education, where this point has been fully applied by working on the creation of a section for women's empowerment in the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research[15]

In the implementation of the National Plan for the Agenda of Women, Security and Peace, this resolution stresses the importance of women's contribution and constitutes an equal in peacekeeping and decision-making, and considered the importance of developing women leaders in higher education and participation in decision-making and working to integrate the concept of gender in the Ministry's plans, the Ministry of Higher Education has adopted programs related to the empowerment of women and in cooperation with all Iraqi universities and colleges and about 36 units have been created in Iraqi public and private universities and colleges in addition to women's empowerment units in The Iraqi Council for Medical Specialties and the Iraqi Organization for Computers and Informatics and others.

These units represent a link between the Women's Empowerment Section and all the Ministry's formations to enforce Security Council Resolution 1325.

It is worth mentioning that the National Plan included a set of key issues and pillars of participation, protection, prevention, promotion, resource mobilization and evaluation of the following topics[16].

1. Women's participation in decision-making and peacebuilding
2. Active participation of women in elections, whether voters or candidates
3. Provision of all health and psychosocial support services to women victims of violence
4. Work to build a culture of gender equality through education and awareness for both sexes
5. Protection, integration and empowerment of displaced women
6. Work to promote and increase employment opportunities for women, including displaced women.
- 7- Work to amend all discriminatory laws in addition to improving the judicial response of women victims of violence.

Conclusion

It is possible to infer the intention of the Security Council by relying on the language used, the discussions that are useful in drafting the resolution, the reference to the provisions of the Charter, and the international laws that are invoked and relied upon. Resolution 1325 contains strong language in many of its provisions. The resolution seeks to support the roles of women in promoting peace and security, which are common objectives of the

Charter of the United Nations. In addition, Resolution 1325 strongly underpins and reflects several key treaties, customary law and jus cogens norms that govern peace and security, war management, and the rights of women and children. In short, Resolution 1325 is binding because it authorizes acts that fall within the purview of the Charter of the United Nations and other international laws. Therefore, as we celebrate the tenth anniversary of the adoption of resolution 1325, it is important to highlight the positive achievements of the solution and the commitments of all relevant stakeholders to support and promote the rights of women and girls during armed conflict.

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Author Information

Dhuha Nashat Namuk
Dijlah University College
